

Too Much of a Good Thing? Australian Cash Transfer Replacement Rates During the Pandemic

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Key findings

We examine Australia's economic policies during the COVID-19 pandemic.

- Australia effectively created a two-tier, 12-month pandemic welfare system during the initial stages of COVID 19, through fiscal transfers that were of unprecedented scope and scale.
- Australia's approach to pandemic transfers proved impossible to sustain over even the initial two-year phase of COVID-19.
- The unevenness of the pandemic response generated inequities.
- Noting that our exercise is descriptive in nature, we raise an important question for future shocks: at what point is there 'too much of a good thing' with crisis cash transfers?

What we knew

- During the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 the Australian federal government temporarily expanded the level and types of fiscal relief available to the working-age population.
- Three of the largest measures were cash transfers targeted at individuals:
 - an \$88 billion wage subsidy;
 - early access to \$38 billion in withdrawals from private pension accounts; and
 - \$52 billion in supplemented benefit payments to the unemployed, students and parents.

What we do

- We combine administrative data on weekly Australian wage earnings with the universe of administrative program records to examine the scope and distributional dimensions of these three emergency COVID-19 cash transfers.

What we find

We provide five stylised facts around the nature of income redistribution during the early part of COVID-19:

1. The scale of fiscal intervention was extensive. In total, 6.5 million working-age Australians (42 per cent of working-age population) accessed the three programs over a 12-month period.
2. The level of transfer per recipient was substantial. The median recipient had 46 per cent of weekly pre-COVID-19 wages replaced by the transfers.
3. There was significant heterogeneity in program receipt. We paint a picture of a two-tier, 12-month pandemic welfare system:
 - (a) A poverty-alleviating income floor through benefit payments was disproportionately accessed by workers in low-earning occupations and welfare recipients.

- (b) The more generous JobKeeper wage subsidy and superannuation withdrawals boosted incomes and provided employment certainty. They were targeted more towards the middle and upper middle segments of the income distribution.
- Together, the programs produced a strong, short-lived, shift in the income distribution. There was large movement out of low levels of income into the lower-middle and upper middle segments of the income distribution. By April 2021, however, the weekly income distribution once again closely resembled the pre-COVID-19 income distribution.
 - The COVID-19 transfers (alongside resilience in earnings) served to increase total gross income flows among the adult Australian population in 2020. As represented in Figure 1.¹ This is notable as income flows generally fall immediately after large adverse shocks.

Figure 1: WEEKLY INCOME FOR THE WORKING AGE POPULATION

What this means for policy

- We expose important macroeconomic trade-offs that were implicit in Australia’s pandemic fiscal strategy.
 - Transfers worth 9 per cent of annual GDP proved impossible to sustain over even the initial two-year phase of COVID-19.
 - The first two waves of COVID-19 in 2020 saw strong protection of incomes. This protection was substantially weaker for subsequent waves in 2021 and 2022.
 - There were inconsistencies in the experience of the same Australians at different ‘waves’ of COVID-19. Transfers also treated Australians in similar positions differently.
 - The support represents a departure from the traditional approach of redistributing from those with a higher capacity to pay to those with lower capacities.
- We raise an important question for decision-makers facing future shocks: at what point is there ‘too much of a good thing’ with crisis cash transfers?

¹The working-age Australian population has been constructed as those aged 16–65 who possess a superannuation balance prior to COVID-19. Source: Single Touch Payroll, COVID-19 program records.

Caveats

- We urge caution in interpreting these observations and the suitability of pandemic policy.
- Descriptive exercises (such as this) do not provide information about the ‘impact’ of policies and are limited to what they directly measure.
- They do not construct counterfactuals (the Australian economy would likely have looked very different in the absence of ameliorating measures) or identify mechanisms of effect.
- We are reliant on indicators that reveal direct, rather than indirect, income consequences.
- We do not measure indirect macroeconomic effects of confidence-assuring action.

Where to now?

- Our research provides insights about the intended and unintended effects of stimulus policy through cash transfers in response to crises.
- Our research suggests that a stronger, principles-based approach around the ways governments will restrict people’s economic engagement in response to external events and towards the targeting of support through cash transfers, might be desirable.
 - It is impossible to know how long a crisis event will last at the onset of a crisis and at the point when initial crisis measures are being enacted.
 - That noted, better alignment between the best available estimates of shock duration (including a strategy that accounts for contingencies in the event the crisis is prolonged or becomes more severe) and the profile of fiscal (and monetary) support - with transfers delivered on a consistent basis across the entire duration of shock – offers a welfare-improving prospect.
 - Related issues such as addressing a seeming public expectation that large, upfront spending commitments accompany every modern shock, and designing state-specific crisis policy tools such as clawback mechanisms for instances when such announcements are made but not appropriate, warrant attention.

More information

- Get the published paper here: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/1467-8462.12501>
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
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